

Business models for Open Educational Resources: how to exploit OER after a funded project?

Guntram Geser
Sandra Schön
Salzburg Research, Innovation Lab
Austria
guntram.geser@salzburgresearch.at
sandra.schoen@salzburgresearch.at
Martin Ebner
Graz University of Technology
Austria
martin.ebner@tugraz.at

Abstract: Open Educational Resources (OER) projects often face the challenge of how to sustain and develop further the resources after the initial project funding comes to an end. OER are provided for free and open for anybody to re-use, modify and distribute. How than can the producers exploit the resources, are there any feasible business models, especially models which could remove or at least reduce dependence on limited and insecure funding? This article presents results of a survey of literature on OER business models and an overview of models identified in the literature. For projects which developed a learning program with OER the freemium model is being considered as a promising model.

1. Introduction: OER as a challenge for exploitation of project results

Open Educational Resources, short OER, are any learning and teaching materials that are provided for free and can be used under an open license (e.g. Creative Commons BY). In addition to free access and easy re-use it is important to note that OER are intended to promote participation in education and support open educational practices (Geser, 2007). As many teachers are still not familiar with the concept of OER, didactic centers of universities and organizations for continuing professional development can play a key role to foster its take-up. Especially important is guidance on how to address copyright issues and use of open licenses for own educational material (Ebner et al., 2016).

OER go against the grain of traditional forms of education as well as copyright constraints that impede the open and creative use of learning resources in classrooms and higher education. These barriers come on top of restrictions set by copyright law in many European and other countries to legitimately use pieces of published media or artistic content in an educational setting (Nobre, 2017).

OER have a high potential for innovation in formal as well as extra-curricular education, however, there are many challenges as well. Our paper addresses the challenge of projects which received initial funding to develop OER for a learning program and need to consider how the project partners can sustain and develop further the resources. OER are provided for free and open for anybody to re-use, modify and distribute. How than can the producers exploit the resources, are there any feasible business models?

Questions of sustainability and exploitation often come up in research and innovation projects funded from European programs and others where the partners are expected to carry forward the project results. In our case, the EU-funded project DOIT - Entrepreneurial Skills for Young Social Innovators in an Open Digital World (October 2017–September 2020), OER of the DOIT learning program will be the core products. In a nutshell, DOIT trials a new approach aimed to empower young people (6–16 years old), together with educators, to co-create in

makerspaces innovative solutions for societal issues. The DOIT OER supports the creative process by fostering digital, social and entrepreneurial competences of the participants (Hornung-Prähauser et al., 2018).

2. Research questions and approach

The OER of the DOIT creative learning program are provided under the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY 4.0) license, which allows unrestricted re-use, except that the project and individual creators must be recognized. Not available under this license, but CC BY-ND (NoDerivatives), is content such as images or videos showing children, which will not be considered here. The open approach of the DOIT project does not impede exploitation of the OER by DOIT partners, but makes it difficult because the products are freely available, there is no copyright protection, and others can try exploiting them as well. Therefore, strategies and business models need to be investigated which might work in such a situation.

The research questions we are exploring are: Which business models for OER have been identified, especially models which could remove or at least reduce dependence on limited and insecure funding? Are there models which could more likely than others work for OER initiatives such as DOIT?

We investigated the question of which business models for OER have been identified by looking into relevant publications of (mostly) OER community members since the start of the OER movement over 10 years ago. In a second step, the project partners will explore exploitation strategies around the most promising business model identified. Below we present results from our survey of literature on OER business models, followed by an overview of business model options considered in the literature, and a summary of key points for the exploitation of OER projects like DOIT.

3. OER business models identified

Many publications touched upon the topic of OER business models as a part of one or more case studies of OER initiatives, often addressing the question of how to expand and sustain them with additional funding and/or more contributors, while discussion of different models is surprisingly rare. It appears that many community/ volunteer-based initiatives and available funding by governments and foundations and/or from internal resources of educational institutions left little room for considering a wider range of feasible business models. As an example, Petrides & Limes (2008) described six OER projects in different parts of the world of which only three considered long-term sustainability: One project in the United States had the ambitious “business model” of establishing a fund of US\$ 2.5 million in order to sustain from the interest their basic operation. Two projects in Africa were struggling to secure public or private grants without considering other options.

While side-lining as long as possible other or additional options to funding streams was the approach of many initiatives, some publications made clear that there are such options worth to consider. Business models suggested by these publications are summarized in Table 2 in the next section.

Still one of the best overviews of a wider range of OER business models can be found in Downes (2007, pp.34-36). Together with two other papers commissioned by the OECD Centre for Educational Research and Innovation (Dholakia et al., 2006, Wiley, 2006) it provided a basis for a chapter on sustainability issues in the first major OECD report on OER (OECD 2007, pp.87-98). While the chapter urged initiatives to consider thoroughly their long-term sustainability, looking for different financing options, it did not address the full range of OER business options/models presented by Downes (2007).

Another publication relevant in this regard is by Guthrie et al. (2008) who described revenue generation options with a focus on online academic resources. Their report was for the not-for-profit organization Ithaka (USA) which helps the academic community use digital technologies to advance research and teaching in sustainable ways; in 2014 Ithaka issued an update of the report (Maron, 2014).

The overview by Guthrie et al. (2008, pp.26-53) includes as direct beneficiaries pay options: Subscription or one-time payment, Pay-per-use, Contributor pays model; as indirect beneficiaries pay options: Host institutional funds/in-kind contributions, Corporate sponsorships, Advertisers, Build diverse streams of philanthropic funding, and Leveraging content through licensing. The 2014 update in addition especially considers “freemium” models in which some resources are provided for free with the aim to move users to pay for added value products or services.

Draft – originally published in: Geser, G., Schön, S. & Ebner, M. (2019). Business models for Open Educational Resources: how to exploit OER after a funded project?. In J. Theo Bastiaens (Ed.), *Proceedings of EdMedia + Innovate Learning* (pp. 1519-1525). Amsterdam, Netherlands: Association for the Advancement of Computing in Education (AACE). Retrieved July 14, 2019 from <https://www.learntechlib.org/primary/p/210171/>

This report also discusses some models in greater detail and includes short case studies on more recent examples (Maron 2014).

Stacey (2012) describes several examples of business options for an “economics of open”, and in 2015 launched an Open Business Model Canvas initiative inviting OER projects to develop and share a canvas (Creative Commons, 2015). In the DOIT project we also use a Business Model Canvas as a tool for discussing and thinking through various aspects such as value propositions, key resources and activities, partners, relationships with users, dissemination channels, etc.

De Langen & Bitter-Rijkema (2012) and De Langen (2013) criticize that earlier attempts to identify a potentially sustainable OER business model, especially among revenue based models, ignored the complexity of such a model as revealed by Business Canvas Modelling. They suggest an OER exchange network with a central hub through which educational institutions share their OER, while benefiting from value network effects. The suggestion appears to be motivated by their background in the Open University Netherlands, which is a sustaining member of the Open Education Consortium. However, around that time according to Janssen et al. (2012) the university offered “open” only some short courses for marketing purposes; they present results of a survey on three OER levels the university might go for, 100%, 10%, or stick to the current level.

Going beyond the usual methods of case studies, Okoli & Wan (2015) employed the Delphi method to identify relevant business models for OER. In three Delphi rounds 19 experts in OER and online education identified 18 models of which they considered ten as relevant for OER.

In 2015, OECD’s Centre for Educational Research and Innovation again published a large report on OER as a catalyst for innovation. The report contains a chapter on how to secure the sustainability of OER initiatives (Orr et al. 2015, pp.109-126). It does not provide new insights but summarizes requirements and measures of success of three basic models: Community-based, Philanthropy-based, and Revenue-based (commercial). Furthermore the report considers an Institutional (hybrid) model which uses OER to receive government or philanthropic support and/or attract more fee-paying students. For each of the three basic models the report describes which resources are needed, where challenges lie, and how the success of the model can be measured (see Table 1).

	Community-based Model	Philanthropy-based Model	Revenue-based Model
Scarce Resource	Engagement of community members	Donors and funding volume for specific purposes of the OER	Revenue from users or other sources
Challenge	Extension and mainstreaming may disenfranchise original contributors Central management and control of OER quality	Donors funding is time limited Donors determine some objectives	Offering OER for free might decrease size of own market
Measures for Success	Size of community Dynamism of community	Sustained funding Keeping community objectives	Sufficient revenues to stay in the business

Table 1. OER sustainability models. Adapted from Orr et al., 2015, p.111, Figure 10.1.

The report gives examples for each model. Some examples illustrate a shift towards a mixed model, in particular community-based OER initiatives which added income generating methods to secure sustainability. The authors expect that OER provision will increasingly be based on mixed models.

Recently the International Council for Open and Distance Education (ICDE) conducted a large survey of how higher education providers from more than thirty countries across the world are using open online approaches to improve teaching and learning. The survey found that of 69 cases around 80% use some OER as a part of their course provision (Orr et al. 2018, p.22).

The chapter on business models addresses five strategies which are based on the empirical results of the survey (Orr et al. 2018: 33-42). Understanding learning products and services as the core of education provision, especially in the case of open and distance learning providers, the following models are distinguished: “fixed core”

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(27 cases), “entrepreneurial with fixed core” (21), “entrepreneurial” (11), “outreach” (6) and “service-provider” (4). Furthermore the study distinguishes between defender- and prospector-like approaches with regard to seven dimensions of the business model: Products and services, Target group, Communication channels, Networks, Legacy or new value chain, Competitive advantage, Profitability and sustainability.

Educational institutions which focus on a traditional fixed core, outreach or service provision are seen as more defensive. But these may still be innovative in some respects, e.g. target groups and new communication channels in the case of an outreach focus. In general, the study results suggest that the surveyed institutions “*are particularly innovative around their core products and services, rather than being innovative with them*” (Orr et al., 2018, p.42). Obviously, innovative activities around a fixed core are less risky than a more entrepreneurial, perhaps disruptive approach regarding the institutional core business. The 11 institutions with a distinct entrepreneurial approach demonstrate innovative strategies in the area of products and services combined with new target groups and communication channels, in other respects they are very diverse.

4. Overview of business models

In the literature of the OER community there is generally little consideration of exploitation of OER in a commercial sense. The reasons for this are that OER are usually provided to all learners openly and free of charge, and the assumption that such resources should be financed by public or philanthropic funds. Therefore the discussion focuses not on exploitation but how projects and institutions can sustain the provision of the OER, after they have been created with some initial funding and/or a volunteering group of providers.

Table 2 gives an overview of business model options considered as suitable for OER in publications which address a range of options (Downes, 2007, Guthrie et al., 2008, Maron, 2014, Okoli & Wan, 2015, Stacey, 2012). Some of the options are not appropriate for the free OER but for added value products and services,

Business Models	Brief Description
Community-based	In-kind contribution of content or support of activities by community members; the community of practice maintains and extends the OER (this model often depends on a few highly committed core people)
Institutional	An organization assumes responsibility for maintaining the OER in-kind, aligned with their overall mission and core business; education/training organizations can incorporate the OER as a free element of their otherwise paid or sponsored course offering
Governmental/NGO	Subsidies or grants by a governmental agency or larger NGO; such funding can be significant but is often unstable due to shifting policy priorities
Philanthropic	Subsidies or grants by foundations, smaller donations by individuals (e.g. crowd-funding)
Endowment	Financial contributions by one or several parties to a fund, interest earned on the fund finances the OER provision
Membership	Annual contribution to a membership organization (financial or an agreed amount of support work or service provision); the organization manages the maintenance, extension and quality assurance of a shared collection of OER
Partnerships	Exchange of complementary resources and knowledge among a group of partners (less formal than a membership organization)
Corporate Sponsorship	Acknowledged support of the OER initiative by a company (financial support, cost-free use of services or other)
Advertisers	Paid advertising of third parties is placed on OER content; suitable advertisers must be well chosen (issue of exposing students to advertising)
Contributor Pays	Is a model for open access academic publications not appropriate for individual OER

	contributors; institutional providers may pay for the hosting of larger amounts of OER
Consultancy, Training and Other Support	Support of third parties for using the OER in their programs, especially if the set of OER and activities follow a certain model (e.g. DOIT co-creative social innovation)
Course and/or Certificate Fees	The OER is free but students (or sponsors) pay for the educational program; in some cases the students can learn on their own but pay for the assessment and certificate
Value Added Products or Services	Users do not pay for the OER but added value, for example enriched formats, special tools or services; called freemium or conversion model if the provider actively uses the OER to convert users to customers of the value added products or services
Licensing Value Added Content	Producers who add significant value to openly available OER can try to license the enhanced content to education/training providers

Table 2. Overview of Business Model Options for OER

There is no lack of business model options but each comes with specific requirements as well as advantages and disadvantages. OER projects considering certain options therefore are advised to consult the mentioned and other, more specialized literature on the models.

5. Insights for OER exploitation strategies

Building on the results of our research, especially the table above, we developed a card game to support business modelling. Each business model described in Tab. 2 is one of 14 cards. The cards can be used by single users or groups in workshops as starting point to support the development of a business model for OER projects. The print-out for the card game is published at the DOIT homepage and available under an open license (CC BY international 4.0). We will investigate formats and collect experiences on how to use them in workshop designs in our future work.

Figure 1. Exemplary business model cards (left) and print-out preview (right).

From the surveyed literature the following key points can be summarized:

- OER are often produced based on one-off seed-funding from government or philanthropic donors, and need to develop sustainability strategies when this funding comes to an end.
- OER initiatives nowadays recognize that they cannot only count on public or private funding but at least need to develop a mixed approach, including appropriate other options (sometimes called “integrated” models).

Draft – originally published in: Geser, G., Schön, S. & Ebner, M. (2019). Business models for Open Educational Resources: how to exploit OER after a funded project?. In J. Theo Bastiaens (Ed.), *Proceedings of EdMedia + Innovate Learning* (pp. 1519-1525). Amsterdam, Netherlands: Association for the Advancement of Computing in Education (AACE). Retrieved July 14, 2019 from <https://www.learntechlib.org/primary/p/210171/>

- A variety of options for sustaining OER initiatives exists, but no “one-size-fits-all” approach because of the differences between initiatives regarding goals, types of OER, contexts (e.g. volunteers vs. institutional).
- The perceived complexity of OER business models may have stimulated the recent popularity of Business Canvas Modelling in the community.
- It appears that more initiatives now consider the freemium or conversion model in which the OER is available for free while value added products or services must be paid; this model has often been rejected by the first generation of OER advocates.

Among the existing business models the freemium model could fit for DOIT and similar projects which received initial funding to develop a learning program with OER modules and aim to sustain and exploit it. In this model the OER is freely available so that providing services for third parties to adopt the DOIT learning program is a clear business model candidate. After they have co-developed the program, run it with groups in 10 European countries, and evaluated the outcomes the project partners will be well positioned to provide services for adopters of the program. The services can be consultancy, training and support, customization of the program and modules, learning assessment, program evaluation. Partners who are educational institutions or training providers can of course also include the program in their portfolio.

Acknowledgement & Disclaimer

The DOIT project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 770063. The content of this publication does not reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Responsibility for the information and views expressed in the publication lies entirely with the authors.

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